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Journal of Vibration Engineering

ISSN:1004-4523

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Comparative Seismic Performance Analysis of Tall Buildings with Diagrid Systems

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Abstract: *The diagrid structural system has emerged as a preferred solution for high-rise buildings because of its high lateral stiffness, reduced material usage, and aesthetic flexibility. This study compares the seismic performance of a thirty-storey steel building using two lateral load-resisting systems—(i) a conventional moment-resisting frame and (ii) a perimeter diagrid frame—both modelled in ETABS following IS 875 and IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016. The models' dimensions are the same (30 m × 30 m plan, 3.2 m storey height). Comparative parameters include fundamental period, storey displacement, inter-storey drift, and base shear. Results indicate that diagrid systems exhibit superior lateral stiffness and drift control: fundamental period reduced by ≈ 41 %, top-storey deflection by > 50 %, and inter-storey drift by > 60 %. The 4-module diagrid had the best stiffness and deformation control of all the configurations that were examined. The findings show that the diagrid system can be used in seismically active regions and has the potential to be an affordable alternative to conventional frames.*

Keywords: *Diagrid system; high-rise building; lateral load-resisting system; seismic performance; ETABS analysis.*

1. Introduction

In recent years, the design and construction of high-rise structures have increasingly relied on innovative building technologies to satisfy the needs of urban expansion and development.

27 There are two primary categories of high-rise structures: interior and exterior. The interior
28 systems consist of shear walls, wall frames, core outriggers, and stiff and braced frames. The
29 exterior structural systems can be classified based on their internal and external load transfer
30 mechanisms, such as tubes, grids, or tube-in-tube systems (1,2). By the time (3) had updated
31 the interior system charts, the exterior system charts had also been updated.

32 Additionally, tall buildings are more affected by lateral loads than gravitational loads.
33 Therefore, when tall structures are designed, lateral loads must be assessed since lateral loads
34 are directly proportional to height. Many studies have been conducted to propose novel
35 structural systems to improve the lateral force performance of high-rise structures. Among
36 structural engineers and researchers researching tall buildings, the diagrid has undoubtedly
37 gained considerable attention. According to related research, diagrids have become the most
38 preferred structural system for skyscrapers because of their superior appearance and lateral
39 rigidity (4,5). To sustain horizontal and vertical loads, the structure uses axial deformation of
40 diagonals in triangular configurations on its exterior facade. (6,7) Structural efficiency can be
41 achieved by utilising diagonals as bracing and vertical resisting elements, making buildings
42 with 100-130 stories competitive (1,3).

43 To make efficient use of structural parts, the structural system chosen must meet the design
44 specifications. Tall structures with rigid frame systems should not exceed 20 stories high, as
45 this causes excessive storey drift due to shear racking from the bending of columns and beams.
46 In tall buildings, an extra diagonal or bracing is included in the frame to prevent column and
47 beam bending and lessen storey drift. (8)

48 A diagrid is a kind of space truss that is composed of triangulated truss systems arranged in a
49 perimeter grid. (9) It is composed of horizontal and diagonal elements that intersect. Figure 1
50 shows the Swiss Re in London, the Hearst Tower in New York, and the Capital Gate Tower
51 in Abu Dhabi as well-known examples of diagrid buildings. (9)

52 **Figure 1. Diagrid buildings: (a) Swiss Re in London, (b) Hearst Tower in New York, and**
 53 **(c) Capital Gate Tower in Abu Dhabi. (9)(10)**

54 Ali et al. (1) presented a methodology for the initial design of diagrids with uniform angles,
 55 focusing on their stiffness characteristics and featuring rectangular shapes. The initial findings
 56 indicate that a diagonal angle has been determined, achieving the necessary strength and
 57 stiffness standards while also reducing the overall weight of the structure. Diagonals with an
 58 approximate inclination of 35 degrees effectively resist shear forces, whereas those inclined
 59 at 90 degrees are the most efficient at transferring overturning moments (11,12). Therefore, it
 60 can be inferred that the ideal angle falls within these defined parameters, typically ranging
 61 from 65° to 75° (13,14). The best value is dependent on the interaction between the bending
 62 and shear forces. In tall structures, the bending moment is the more dominant factor, thus
 63 supporting higher optimal angle values.

64 The seismic performance of high-rise buildings is a primary concern in structural engineering,
 65 especially in areas classified as Seismic Zones IV and V as per IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 (15).
 66 Conventional steel moment-resisting frame systems, the most common structural systems,
 67 suffer from high lateral flexibility and increased fundamental time periods, leading to more
 68 storey displacements and interstorey drifts due to seismic loading (8).

69 To maintain compliance with code-specified drift limits, these systems often require large
 70 member sizes and complex ductile detailing, which can increase material usage and
 71 construction costs. Diagrid structural systems, composed of a network of diagonally inclined
 72 steel members forming a triangulated perimeter, have emerged as promising alternatives for

73 high-rise buildings due to their improved lateral stiffness, reduced structural weight, and
74 efficient seismic force resistance through axial action (16,17).

75 Granted, diagrid systems have come to be recognised as structural and architectural boons;
76 however, rigorous comparisons of these building systems with conventional steel frames
77 under seismic excitation, particularly in the Indian design context, have thus far been limited.
78 Hence, there is currently a knowledge gap regarding the applicability of these materials as
79 earthquake-resistant materials in high seismic zones.

80 The objective of this study is to present a comparative analysis of a 30-storey high-rise steel
81 building modelled in ETABS with two unique lateral load-resisting systems: (i) a
82 conventional steel moment-resisting frame and (ii) a perimeter diagrid system. Gravity and
83 wind loads are per IS 875 (Parts 1–3) (18–20), and seismic zones IV and V are per IS 1893
84 (Part 1):2016 (15). A standard plan of 30 m by 30 m is considered. With ETABS software,
85 structural member modelling and analysis were carried out.

86 **2. Methodology**

87 **2.1. Model Development**

88 To construct the diagrid structural model, a grounded vertical cantilever beam that offers a
89 longitudinal division that complies with the diagrid configuration must be used (21). A
90 module is identified by a single diagrid level that spans a specific number of stories, indicated
91 by the letter 'n.' A six-storey diagrid structural module is shown in the model in Figure 2. All
92 the required lateral stiffnesses are assigned to the perimeter diagrids to improve the accuracy
93 of the lateral rigidity estimation provided by the diagrids. (22) The diagonal members are
94 presumed to be pinned. As a result, they can sustain moment-by-axial action and transverse
95 shear. This idealisation helps to ease the design difficulty by identifying the usual cross-
96 sectional areas of the web and flange members for each module. Equations (1) and (2), tailored
97 for each design instance using the design technique suggested by (23), can be used to
98 determine module member sizes.

99

Figure 2: Typical 6-storey diagrid module

$$A_{d,w} = \frac{VL_d}{2N_{d,w}E_d h \gamma \cos^2 \theta} \quad (1)$$

$$A_{d,f} = \frac{2ML_d}{(N_{d,f} + \delta)E_d h \chi \sin^2 \theta} \quad (2)$$

The areas of each diagonal on the web and the flange are denoted by $A_{d,w}$ and $A_{d,f}$, respectively. V represents the shear force. M represents the moment, L_d represents the diagonal length, E_d represents the modulus of elasticity of steel, $N_{d,w}$ represents the number of diagonals on every web plane, $N_{d,f}$ Represents the number of diagonals on each flange plane, δ represents the contribution of the web diagonals to the bending rigidity, B represents the width of the structure along the path of the applied force, q represents the angle of the diagonal members, γ represents the transverse shear strain, and χ represents the curvature. (16,23)

2.2. Building Configuration

A 30-storey structure was modelled and analysed for a diagrid structure (24) and a conventional steel structure. (25) The building's plan area is $30 \text{ m} \times 30 \text{ m}$, with a $12 \text{ m} \times 12 \text{ m}$ central core. The building's overall height is 96 m, with each storey standing 3.2 m tall. Modelling and analysis of the diagrid structures are carried out via ETABS software. The earthquake load is calculated via the following parameters: medium soil, zone factor of 0.2, importance factor of 1, and response reduction factor of 5(15). The floor slab is subjected to a live design load of 4 kN/m^2 (20). The typical configuration and layout of the building are

122 shown in Figures 3 and 4. Table 1 presents the properties of the Diagrid structure and the
 123 conventional structure used for the study. This includes the plan dimensions, the location of
 124 the building, the construction material, and the type of soil.

125
 126 **Figure 3: Building plan**

127 **Figure 4 (a) Elevation of the diagrid structure (b) Elevation of the conventional structure**

128 **Table 1: Properties of the Diagrid structure and conventional structure**

Description	Diagrid Structure	Conventional Structure
Plan Dimension	30 m x 30 m	30 m x 30 m
Interior Column	1000 mm x 1000 mm	-
Exterior Column	-	ISWB 550
Beam	ISMB 500, ISWB 550	ISMB 500

129 **2.3. Analysis of the building**

130 The linear static analysis is also called the equivalent lateral force method. A linear static
131 analysis is a standard method for effective structural design and modelling of a diagrid, a
132 triangulated structural system. A linear static analysis determines structural displacements and
133 stresses, assuming a linear relationship between the applied loads and the structural response.
134 For the linear static analysis stage of the diagrid, the designer assumes the design loads (i.e.,
135 dead loads, live loads, and wind or seismic loads) are applied to the modelling software to
136 establish internal forces and deflections. The most important aspect of linear static analysis is
137 its speed and ease of computational analysis, which allows for quick preliminary design and
138 optimisation of sections. For diagrids specifically, this process is used to verify that the
139 diagonal members and nodes are appropriately sized to transfer axial forces and to justify
140 deflections considered acceptable for use. Although values from linear static analysis provide
141 a reasonable first estimate of the structural response by considering physical phenomena, they
142 do not account for complex behaviour, including material or geometric nonlinearities, which
143 can become more significant under extreme loading conditions. Thus, assessing the
144 displacements of a diagrid system through a linear static analysis is often a first step prior to
145 conducting a nonlinear analysis.

146 **3. Results and Discussion**

147 **3.1. Time Period**

148 Figure 5 shows the fundamental time periods of three structural systems: a conventional
149 structure, a 6-module diagrid structure, and a 4-module diagrid structure. Compared with
150 those of the other systems, the conventional structure has the longest time period of 3.046 s,
151 demonstrating that the structure is less stiff and more flexible. The 6-module diagrid structure
152 has the shortest time period at 2.031 s, and the 4-module diagrid structure has the shortest
153 time period at 1.799 s. The reduction in period from the conventional to the four-module
154 diagrid, which exhibits an increase in global stiffness of about 41%, validates the diagrid's

155 superior rigidity. These findings are consistent with those of Moon (2008) and Asadi and
 156 Adeli (2017), who found that the period decreased as diagonal inclination increased.

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Figure 5: Time periods for the conventional structure and diagrid structure

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3.2. Standard Displacement

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Figure 6 shows the storey-wise displacement profiles for three structural systems: the conventional structure, the 6-module diagrid structure, and the 4-module diagrid structure. The displacement increases with height for all the structures; however, the displacement magnitude varies due to differences in the lateral flexibility and stiffness of the structure. The conventional structure reaches its maximum displacement at the top storey, nearly 110 mm, indicating greater lateral flexibility and less lateral stiffness. The 6-module diagrid structure exhibits lower displacement, with a maximum of approximately 60 mm, indicating that the diagrid system allows greater lateral stiffness than the conventional system. The 4-module diagrid structure has minimal displacement at the top storey, consistently less than 50 mm, indicating that increasing the diagrid angle (fewer modules) results in even greater stiffness and reduced lateral deflection. The diagrid systems reduce top-storey deflection by 55–60 % compared with the conventional frame. The steeper four-module configuration (72° inclination) provides the highest stiffness. Similar performance improvement was observed by Jani and Patel (2013) for steel diagrids exceeding 25 storeys.

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Figure 6: Storey displacement for diagrid and conventional structures

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3.3. Storey Drift

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Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the profiles for storey drift in the X- and Y-directions for three types of structures: the conventional structure, the diagrid structure with six modules, and the diagrid structure with four modules. The conventional structure has the most drift in the X direction, with a peak occurring around the middle of the structure at approximately 0.0025. The Diagrid Structure 6-Modules had less drift, with a peak of roughly 0.0012. The Diagrid Structure 4 module had the least negligible drift, remaining below 0.001. It clearly shows that diagrid systems limit lateral deformation and that the 4-module system has the most extraordinary capacity for stiffness, control, or limiting the relative movement of the floor plates.

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In the Y direction, the trend remains the same. The conventional structure had the most considerable prepack drift, particularly in the X-direction, with a value near 0.0026 at mid-height. The Diagrid Structure 6-Modules had better performance with a moderate maximum drift near 0.0013, whereas the Diagrid Structure 4-Modules had the lowest maximum drift, near 0.0008.

191 Both graphs illustrate that diagrid systems decrease storey drift more than traditional frames
 192 do, whereas fewer diagrid modules (greater diagrid angles) maximise the reduction in
 193 interstorey drift. In regions of seismic risk, the return to obtain diagrids is substantial, as
 194 diagrid systems impact not only structural safety but also the comfort of occupants by
 195 controlling interstorey drift.

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Figure 7: Storey drift in the X direction for diagrid and conventional structures

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Figure 8: Storey drift in the Y direction for diagrid and conventional structures

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4. Conclusion

201 This study focused on the effects of seismic action on diagrid and conventional frame 30-
202 symmetrical live steel structures. After being modelled in ETABS and analysed according to
203 the procedures of IS 1893:2016, the results essentially confirmed the advantages of the diagrid
204 system. When the lateral stiffness increased, the fundamental time period of the building
205 decreased, and the storey displacement, interstorey drift, and acceleration were strongly
206 controlled. These advantages arise principally because of the triangular avenue of diagrids,
207 which permits adequate seismic force redistribution and any additional bracing or heavy beam
208 constructions. Furthermore, the angles of the diagrids affect the displacement response of a
209 building and thus emphasise the importance of geometric optimisation during the design
210 process. In addition to the structural advantages, the diagrid system also provides architectural
211 freedom and reduces material usage by eliminating the need for (perimeter) columns. In
212 general, this means that diagrids are serious competitors to typical frames, especially for high-
213 elevation buildings in high-seismic-risk regions. Further research could focus on nonlinear
214 analysis, long-term behaviour, and cost-effectiveness to fully exploit these factors in practical
215 construction.

216 **5. Funding statement**

217 The authors declare that no particular funding was obtained to carry out this investigation.

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